

CLLOUD-BASED ENTERPRISE RESOURCE PLANNING FOR SUSTAINABLE GROWTH OF SME_s IN THIRD WORLD COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

In this research paper, we have developed a new cloud-based Enterprise Resource Planning System using the Linked Servers technology. Our focus is on Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), seeking for ways of assisting them enjoy the huge benefits of Enterprise Resource Planning and the internet cloud. Our ERP system can integrate key business processes into a single software solution, and enables seamless flow of information from heterogeneous data sources across all functional areas of the organization and beyond. The new system was developed using the prototyping methodology, considered as best suited for a project of this kind due its advantage of active user involvement throughout the development process. Using the questionnaire as our major data gathering instrument, user requirements were gathered from selected SMEs across the south-east geopolitical region of Nigeria to aid our design. A thorough Requirement Analysis was carried out to ensure proper design of the prototype system, and, using the system development life cycle approach, we carried out design of the architectural frameworks for the cloud based ERP system, to illustrate basic layout of application deployment and the synchronization mechanism for data exchange between vendor servers and the central server. Result obtained from our study shows that the new ERP software solution provides improved operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. We recommend the creating of enabling environment by appropriate government authorities, and a systematic implementation of the findings of this research paper by corporate business owners.

Keywords: Internet-cloud, ERP, Vendor servers, SMEs, Data integration.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 The Concept of Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)

Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) is an attempt to integrate key business processes of a firm into a single software solution, whose aim is to enable easy flow of information throughout the organization. Ordinarily, such systems focus more on internal processes, though in some cases, may include transactions with customers, business partners, and vendor companies.

Normally, a large business organization will have dissimilar information systems or software applications built around different functional areas, organizational levels, and business processes, which ordinarily cannot easily exchange information, especially at the point where such information is needed for quick decision making. Most times also, each of the different software application will require a fragmentation of data in hundreds of separate databases, and this can equally degrade efficiency and business performance. A good example is the problem of a Sales Personnel who may not be able to tell (at the time a customer places an order) whether or not the ordered items exist in the inventory store. Also, the Manufacturing unit may find it difficult to carry out their duty of planning for new production due to their inability to easily access sales information at the time they need it.

A good Enterprise Resource Planning system can solve this problem of integration and seamless data exchange across various levels of the organization, and across various functional areas of the business corporation. Such a system will receive data from various key business processes in Production and Manufacturing, Finance and Accounting, Sales and Marketing, Human Resources, and so on, into a central data repository. From the central data repository, information that was previously fragmented in different systems can be shared across all parts of the firm. Undoubtedly, an efficient coordination of these parts will lower a business's operational cost, while increasing customer satisfaction.

A seemingly simple process such fulfilling a customer order as mentioned above, will require an involvement of several functional areas of the business and a free flow of data across the firm, between business partners, and vendors, as well as customers.

There are existing ERP software solutions which are mainly products of such Software Vendors like SAP, Oracle, and Microsoft. Some of these software include: SAP's Business Suite, Oracle's e-Business Suite, Microsoft's Dynamic Suite, and so on. Most of these software solutions however, target very large multinational business corporations. Over the years, not much attention has been given to Small and Medium scale Enterprises (SMEs) to find ways of helping them enjoy the huge benefits of ERP.

In a bid to solve the data exchange and web application integration problem using Enterprise Resource Planning software, software vendors have always made use of Web Services and a collection of web services popularly known as Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA) to integrate various software systems into one. Service-Oriented Architecture is a set of self-contained services that communicate with each other to create a working software application. On the other hand, a web service is a collection of open protocols and standards used for data exchange between applications or systems. Furthermore, these web services are self-contained, modular applications that can be described, published, located and invoked over a network, generally the World Wide Web [1].

Although the use of web services can provide a near flexible solution to the problem of application integration [9], the service architecture is confronted with a number of stubborn problems including the issue of data security [7], and the challenge of synchrony of web services [11]. With the use of WSDL and UDDI in web services, an attacker can access any publicly available WSDL file and tamper with it. Such attacks can be in the form of WSDL Scanning or WSDL tampering. The former scans the WSDL file and exposes some operational and even confidential information. According to [1], protection against these threats is not easy with typical methods like authentication and authorization.

There is need to design efficacious ERP solution that can enable business owners to streamline and automate tedious back office tasks. Apart from streamlining and automating back office tasks, managers can equally get real-time visibility into the inner workings of their operations and motivate employees to be more productive, focused, and successful towards performing their roles. A focus on cloud-based ERP will encourage small and medium scale enterprises to take advantage of cloud computing which delivers computing services such as servers, storage, database, networking, software, as well as analytical and business intelligence to corporate business owners at a very low cost. With the internet cloud, a small scale company will not have to purchase the software, hardware, servers and facilities necessary to run her ERP and there will be no need to train and maintain an IT team that is responsible for the software. All that is needed are computers that can access the internet. Since the cloud host/vendor offers the maintenance of infrastructure, there will be reduced operational cost for such SMEs.

In this research paper therefore, we shall design a cloud-based Enterprise Resource Planning System for efficient data exchange and web application integration using the Linked Servers technology. Our focus will be on Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) to seek ways of assisting them enjoy the huge benefits of such technology-based systems, with very little operational costs. Being on the cloud, the system will be directly managed off-site by a third party provider and with the ability to address diverse data sources similarly.

1.2 Objectives of Study

In this research paper, the Linked Servers technology is adopted in the design of Cloud-based Enterprise Resource Planning which aims to guarantee efficient data exchange and web application integration to ensure rapid and sustainable growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs) in developing countries. The study will achieve the following:

- i. Discover major weaknesses of existing ERP systems in meeting business needs of SMEs.
- ii. Propose a Cloud-based ERP model using Linked Servers technique to provide efficient and secure data synchronization between heterogeneous vendor database servers.
- iii. Ensure distributed queries, updates, and transactions on dissimilar data sources across the enterprise.
- iv. Make recommendations to assist local SMEs enjoy the huge benefits of ERP and the competitive business advantages of the internet cloud.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

This section seeks to review existing literature on concepts, theories and empirical studies that border on Enterprise Resource Planning, Executive Support Systems, Cloud Computing, and the Linked Servers Technology Architecture. We will begin with a conceptual framework to discuss various perceptions relating to our topic of study.

2.1. Definition of Enterprise Resource Planning

According to [15], an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) a business process management software that enables an organization to use a system of integrated applications in managing her business. Normally, such a system will make use of tools and applications that cover all areas of the business and enables potential communication from various sources.

The software will also seeks to automate many back-office functions related to technology, services and human resources. With ERP Software, all essential business functions such as estimation, finance, human resources, production, marketing, sales, purchasing, and others can be collected at a central source. From here, data can be easily accessed by the concerned persons and departments. Enterprise resource planning system can also streamline the assemblage, storage and usage of an organization's data in a most unified way. ERP system efficiently intermingles all components of business procedures and methods, which consist of development, product planning, manufacturing, sales and marketing, and others, in a single database, application and user interface. Such Enterprise Resource Planning system is reckoned to be a type of enterprise application that is created to be used by large-scale businesses and it oftentimes requires devoted teams to analyze and customize the data to handle deployment and upgrades of the software [15].

Today, majority of corporate organizations implement ERP systems for a number of reasons. In fact, a study conducted in 2016 by Panorama Consulting Solutions, LLC, reveals some reasons why organizations implement ERP systems. Their report shows the following reasons, by percentage:

- To replace out-of-date ERP software (49%)
- For replacing accounting software (15%)
- To replace other non-ERP systems / had no system (20%)
- To replace homegrown systems (16%) (Panorama Consulting Solutions, 2016).

According to the report also, organizations that have never implemented ERP System will surely need one for the following reasons:

- To improve internal business processes
- In order to improve company performance
- For reducing IT expenses and labor costs
- To improve interactions between internal employees and external organizations. (Panorama Consulting Solutions, 2016).

However, ERP applications for small-scale businesses can be designed as a lightweight business management software which can be customized for particular business industry. With a functioning Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) in place, crucial issues can easily be resolved which could be damaging to the organization if left unchecked.

2.2. Why ERP is Indispensable for Growth of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs)

Before now, an all-in-one solution software was not in existence which could help organizations in managing their business process, but as technology grows, Software Developers has seen the need to introduce the ERP technology. ERP solution can be a wonderful management tool when it comes to maintaining and managing businesses in a most efficient way, and this ideology can only get better with time. A well-designed Enterprise Resource Planning, such as the one being proposed in this research project, can perfectly bring key business processes together and allow small and medium scale enterprises as well as large business organizations make data-driven decisions, improve collaboration, and strengthen business productivity. As a matter of fact, ERP can be made to covers all functional areas of a company, which include the following: finance, human resources, customer relationship management, manufacturing, and supply chain.

2.2.1. Finance

Modern Enterprise Resource Planning systems offer dashboards that give users an overview of their current financial status, and with this they can tap into real-time business data anytime, anywhere. For small businesses, ERP can assist managers track income and expenses and record transactions and account structures. It can also create financial documents like profit and loss statements and balance sheets.

2.2.2. Human Resources (HR)

Some modern ERP software can enable SMEs to manage company data and help in streamlining employee management tasks such as hiring, payroll, and other duties. Small businesses can take advantage of ERP to automate payroll processing, track employee attendance to work, and manage employee records like performance reviews, payroll benefits, and scheduling. Self-service functionalities can equally allow employees to request time off or view their attendance record. One good thing about an ERP is that it can help managers to save time, energy, and the risk-factor because they could track each employee's performance and pinpoint HR problems before they start to happen.

2.2.3. Customer Relationship Management

A good ERP can help SMEs manage customer contact information, order histories, invoices, and quotes.

2.2.4. Manufacturing

A well designed Enterprise Resource Planning solution can optimize project and cost management as well as production planning. This feature can improve factors that play prominent part in automating

daily processes and business communication. It can offer manufacturers the ability to manage resources by accessing real-time data and fulfil customer needs by providing fast and reliable services.

2.2.5. Supply chain

ERP is a good manager of the Supply Chain. It can help manage the flow of goods and services from raw material acquisition to delivery of the finished product to the customer. Most SMEs today are still in the habit of entering information by hand while striving to track down the inventory present in her warehouse. In the case of such SMEs, implementing an ERP is quite indispensable. With such a smart solution, business owners can save money and time by automating all its major business processes. Modern solutions also offer dashboards and business intelligence to help these SMEs handle most of their inventory management problems.

2.3. Cloud-based ERP Systems for Small Businesses

Some ERP solutions are marketed as being only for small businesses. These solutions can be on-premise or web-based; though, web-based is more common for small businesses due to the generally lower upfront cost. ERP software for only small businesses is less complex and has limited functionality to cut costs and tailored to meet the needs of smaller companies.

Research has shown that most ERP solutions represented as free on the WWW are meant to be more of a demo than a permanent solution. There are usually some costs associated with these systems to add functionality that are required for interested businesses or installation and maintenance fees. According to Panorama Consulting Solutions (2016), some examples of free and open source small business ERP software include:

- Odoo: The free plan, Odoo Community, is an open-source ERP software that incorporates the following applications: CRM, invoicing, expense tracking, e-Commerce, appointment scheduling, and POS. With a special link, this ERP software can equally integrate with heavy applications like eBay or USPS.
- Dolibarr: A free open source ERP system that features CRM, HR management, CMS, inventory control, marketing automation, and project management.

2.4. The Linked Servers Technology

According to [5], Linked Servers technology makes it possible for an SQL Server to “talk” to another ODBC compliant database, such as another SQL Server instance or an Oracle database, with a direct T-SQL query. It can enable one to execute distributed queries against tables stored in a Microsoft SQL Server instance and another data store. It is easy to use the Microsoft SQL Server Management Studio to link a data store to an SQL Server instance and then execute distributed queries against both data stores.

Linked servers can be created using the SQL Server Management Studio. From the Object Explorer pane, expand the "Server Objects" section, right click on "Linked Servers" and choose "New Linked Server" from the menu.

SQL Server can be linked to any server provided it has OLE-DB provider from Microsoft to allow a link. Example, Oracle has an OLE-DB provider for oracle that Microsoft provides to add it as linked server to SQL Server group.

Figure 1: Basic Linked Servers Configuration Architecture (source: Eric Blinn in Edgewood Solutions Guide, 2021).

2.5. Improving Privacy and Data Security Level in Cloud-Based ERP Systems

Nowhere is security more of a concern than with cloud-based ERP applications. Many businesses assume that after they move their ERP system to cloud, the security is beyond control. But, there are proactive steps that businesses can take to help them gain more control over their cyber security. Despite the security risks, businesses have good reasons for moving their ERP systems to the cloud. In addition to 24 hours cloud-based access to data across multiple departments and geographical locations. According to [13], competitiveness is another clear reason.

3. METHODOLOGY AND USER REQUIREMENT ANALYSIS FOR THE NEW SYSTEM

For this study, the prototyping model was used for early development of our proposed cloud based enterprise resource planning. Prototyping is a software development model in which a software prototype is developed, evaluated, and re-designed until an acceptable prototype is achieved. The accepted prototype is then used as the basis of development of the final system.

Software prototyping works best in situations where user requirements are not fully known at the onset. User involvement, especially the continuous interaction between system users and system developers makes it the most preferred method for the task of this study.

The figure 2 shows the prototyping model, which allows for quick design of an early system after initial requirements gathering from system users. The prototype is then subjected to an evaluation process using appropriate test data. The evaluation aims at allowing users to put the system into use in order to identify additional user requirements or any need to improve on existing ones. Evaluation and testing continues until all identified user requirements are fully met.

Figure 2: A popular prototyping model (source: www.geeksforgeeks.org)

Finally, the prototyping model will be integrated into the wider system development approach which include the different phases of software development life cycle, and will be adopted for this study. The major phases of development include the following: System definition, data gathering / analysis, system design, implementation, testing, and system maintenance phase.

3.1 Data Gathering and Requirement Analysis

The questionnaire method was used to gather data for development of our proposed system. The purpose of the data gathering, however, is to generate user requirements to aid our design.

About 300 copies of questionnaire were administered to Business Entrepreneurs, as well as management staff of selected Small and Medium size Enterprises in the south-east geopolitical region of Nigeria.

Some of these SMEs include Hotels, grocery stores, garages, etc., that serve a hyper local target audience, and operate with less than a certain level of workforce and assets. Our goal was to ensure accurate and honest information gathering and user requirements to aid our system design process.

In order to gather relevant user requirements for our proposed ERP system, structured questions were posed to elicit information in the following areas:

- i. **Need for accessibility of common company data:** Most SMEs in developing countries are accustomed to spreadsheet accounting and some manual business processes using outdated data sources. Therefore, the following questions were posed:
 - Do you need a system that compiles and stores company common data as well as make it readily accessible to you?
 - Do you wish to gain real business insight for informed decision making?
 - Would you like to view, manage, and track core business processes and resources in real-time using a single data source?
- ii. **Integration of core business functions:** The following questions were posed:
 - Do you need a system of shared database to support and connect multiple business activities?
 - Do you wish to integrate business functionality for accounting, inventory management, order processing, human resources etc.?
 - Do you require integration and collaboration across departments?
 - Do you require improved inventory management?
 - Do you think your company requires standardized business processes?
- iii. **Cloud-based ERP system:** Business owners and top managers were asked the following question: Whom will you select as your preferred software partner or vendor, or do you prefer a cloud-based system?
 - Do you wish to leverage on global markets?
- iii. **ERP components and basic features:** The following questions were posed:
 - Which processes of your business do you wish to incorporate into an ERP system?
 - What features do you think you will need your ERP to have as a start?
- v. **Legacy systems:** In order to gather user requirements in the area of legacy systems and applications, the following questions were asked:
 - Do you wish to replace your legacy systems?
 - Do you wish to reposition your company for sustainable growth and development?
 - Do you require improved customer service and operational efficiency?
- vi. **Operational cost and business scalability:** The following question was asked in the area of operational cost and business scalability:
 - Do you want to experience reduced cost of business operations?
 - Do you require an ERP system that scales up as your business grows?
 - What are your projected performance enhancements based on your expectations and user preferences?

Ninety five percent (95%) of all questions were answered in the affirmative, showing the need for cloud based enterprise resource planning systems for sustainable growth and development of small and medium scale enterprises in third world countries.

All information and user requirements were gathered from business entrepreneurs, top management cadre of country SMEs, directors, section managers, and supervisors, and from the information gathered during this stage, we were able to establish the following:

- a. Cloud-based ERP is required for sustainable growth of SMEs in developing countries.
- b. Existing ERP systems and businesses have major weaknesses in meeting the needs of SMEs.
- c. There is need to ensure data synchronization between heterogeneous vendor database servers in order to ensure efficient information exchange.
- d. There is need to implement distributed database that updates data in remote vendor databases in an efficient and secure manner.
- e. There is need for automated data back-up in the cloud as safeguard against data loss due to vendor services malfunction or crash of central server machine.

4. SYSTEM DESIGN, RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

In this section, we present the technical architecture which basically defines layout of layers of application deployment between servers and client computers, interfaces, platforms and emerging technologies that will provide technical functionality for our proposed cloud based enterprise resource planning system.

4.1. Architecture of the Proposed Cloud based ERP System for Sustainable Growth of SMEs

The figure 4 depicts the architecture of the proposed cloud based ERP system for sustainable growth of SMEs, especially in developing countries. It is a conceptual framework the shows basic layout of application deployment and various activities involved in the new system, and illustrates the synchronization mechanism for data exchange between vendor servers and the central server.

Figure 4. Architecture of the Proposed Cloud based ERP System for SMEs.

4.2. Algorithms for Inventory Management Module of the proposed ERP system

The basic algorithms for inventory management module of our proposed ERP system is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Unified Inventory management algorithms for the proposed based ERP system

4.3. High Level Model for Accounting Management Subsystem

The High Level Model for Accounting Management subsystem of our proposed ERP system is shown in figure 6.

Figure 6. Integrated accounting model for the proposed based ERP system

4.4. System Implementation and Discussions

Here, we discuss some of the development tools used in the implementation of our new design to guarantee efficient and secure data synchronization among vendor databases from remote locations. The following sections of the new system were implemented using the under listed programming tools:

Database Synchronization and Exchange: Linked Servers Technology was used to create synchronization mechanism and database connectivity for exchange between vendor servers and the central server.

User Management Module: The ASP.NET was used to create the user management session for administering the central server.

Central server database: My-SQL server technology was adopted for design of the central server database.

Vendor server 1: My-SQL, an open source database management system, was used to develop a relational database to store data for the Inventory management subsystem, which included such information as Inventory Management System Report Types such as list of stock items, list of sold items, list of returned items, report date filter, category, price, and quantity.

Vendor server 2: MS-SQL was used to develop a relational database to store data for the Accounting management subsystem, which included such information as Account report category and information including Account Expenses, Purchases, Sales, Point-of-Sale records, and summary report information. Others include dates of transaction, transaction description, transaction receipt number, and sales personnel's remarks.

Data Migration from various platforms to the remote server: My-SQL workbench, an open source development tool was used to export databases from other platforms to the My-SQL-based remote server. Another is the My-SQL connector for ODBE, which is a connector tool used to create an interface between the central MY-SQL server and all other database platforms that are compatible with open database connectivity technology.

Inventory Management subsystem: Visual Studio 2015 was used to implement the Inventory Management System. Some of the tools include: C# for the front end and application logic development, and ADO.NET for relational database connectivity.

Accounting Management Subsystem: VB.NET was used to implement the Accounting Management subsystem.

Web Hosting: The IIS and the APACHE web servers were adopted for hosting our web applications built with the .NET technology.

4.4.1. Results

The output screens in figure 7 and figure 8 show some of the results of the implementation.

Figure 7. Output screen illustrating the synchronization mechanism for data exchange between vendor servers and the central server.

Figure 8. Some output screen from the accounting management subsystem and the inventory management subsystem.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1. Conclusion

In this research paper, we have developed a cloud-based Enterprise Resource Planning System for efficient data exchange and web application integration using the Linked Servers technology. Our focus was on Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMEs), seeking for ways of assisting them enjoy the benefits of Enterprise Resource Planning. With such an integrated system on the cloud, there will be very little operational cost on the part of the SMEs because most of the institutional and IT infrastructure will be directly managed off-site by a third party provider.

Again, the system will encourage small and medium scale enterprises to take advantage of cloud computing which delivers such computing services as servers, storage, database, networking, software applications, and analytical and business intelligence to corporate business owners at a very low cost. Our system can integrate key business processes of a firm into a single software solution, which enables seamless flow of information throughout the organization and beyond. It can solve the problem of integration and seamless data exchange across heterogeneous data sources at various levels of organization, and across all functional areas of a business corporation. It has the ability to receive data from key business processes in Production and Manufacturing, Finance and Accounting, Sales and Marketing, Inventory and Human Resources, and so on, into a single central data repository, from where information can be shared among various stakeholders as the need arises.

The new system was developed using the prototyping methodology, considered as best suited for a project of this kind due to its iterative nature and user involvement. The questionnaire method was used to gather all user requirements from selected SMEs across the south-east geopolitical region of Nigeria to aid our design. A thorough Requirement Analysis was carried out to ensure proper design of the prototype system.

Result obtained from our study shows that the new ERP software solution provides improved operational efficiency and customer satisfaction.

5.2. Recommendations

We recommend the creation of enabling business environment by appropriate government authorities, and a systematic implementation of the findings of this research paper by corporate business owners. The system is a new attempt to ensure rapid growth and sustainability of our Small and Medium sized Enterprises by harnessing the benefits of ERP and the internet cloud. There is need for a concerted effort by all stake holders, government agencies, corporate organizations, and business owners to take advantage of the opportunities offered by the emergence of the internet and Information Technology to improve the business sector.

References

- [1] Aruna S. (2016): Security in Web Services-Issues and Challenges, International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology, Vol 5, issue 09, September 2016.
- [2] Baburajan, Rajani (2011): "The Rising Cloud Storage Market Opportunity Strengthens Vendors". It.tmcnet.com. Retrieved 2018-12-02.
- [3] Daniel M., Adnan M., & Rakibul H. (2015): "Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) Systems: Design, Trends, and Deployment, The International Technology Management Review, Vol. 5 (2015), No. 2, 72-81.
- [4] Davenport T. (1998). Putting Enterprise into the Enterprise System, Harvard Business Review, 76(4),121-131

- [5] Eric Blinn (2021): Understanding SQL Server Linked Servers, Edgewood Solutions, LLC , 2021
- [6] Fripp C. (2010): Cloud vs. Hosted services, what's The Difference? IT News Africa Available via <http://www.itnewsafrika.com/2011/04/cloud-vs-hosted-services/> [accessed October 30, 2020].
- [7] Hongbing Wang, and Joshua Zhexue Huang (2004): Web services: problems and future directions, Journal of Web Semantics, Volume 1, Issue 3, April 2004, Pages 309-320
- [8] Jaideep M., Ram Subramanian & Pradeep G. (2021): "Critical factors for successful ERP implementation: Exploratory findings from four case studies", Elsevier B.V., vol. 56, Issue
- [9] Kennet C. Laudon and Jane P. Laudon (2010): Management Information Systems, eleventh edition.
- [10] Lin, A. And Chen, N. C. (2012): Cloud computing as an innovation: Perception, attitude and adoption International Journal of Information Management. Vol. 4 No. 1
- [11] Miko Matsumaru (2006): Ten Top Web Services "Issues",
- [12] Moller, C. (2005). ERP II: a conceptual framework for next-generation enterprise systems? Journal of Enterprise Information Management, 18(4), 483-497
- [13] Owens S.J., (2018): Planning for Attack: Security and cloud based ERP. Enterprise Software by ERP Desk.
- [14] Raheela Nasim et al (2020): "A Cloud-Based Enterprise Resource Planning Architecture for Women's Education in Remote Areas", Electronics, September 2020
- [15] Rafi Ahmed K. (2017): "Detailed Introduction to Enterprise Resource Planning", Computer Information Services (CIS), Software House, 2017.
- [16] Wang (2012): "Enterprise Cloud Service Architectures". Information Technology and Management. **13** (4): 445–454. doi:10.1007/s10799-012-0139-4. S2CID 8251298.
- [17] www.geeksforgeeks.org